

Individual Assignment 2

Human Resource Management BB-2208

Case Study Analysis

The Fombrun Model

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Abstract

Models are hugely an HRM distinguishing characteristics. The models provide an empirical structure for researching HRM giving an analytical framework that identify certain practices of HRM and factors of key problems. This paper looks at management in effective performance level, to provide maximum organisation output and investigating the HRM processes. Firstly, the findings of this study the process of The Fombrun Model. Next is to identify the key problems of the case study. It is then to analyze the key issues of the HRM practices theory by using the analytical tool model (The Fombrun Model). Afterwards, supported by the optimal strategy and rational evaluation of the strengths and disadvantages of the solutions to the organisation.

Introduction

With many organisations using Human Resources practices to manage the business effectively in which it may enhance a more capable workforce that can achieve the goals of the organisation. HR practices plays an important role in any industry including agriculture ranging from managing its farmers and managers. HR activities has led to the development and success that gives a very significant effect a company. This led to the development of HRM models and the relationship with business processes, established by Legge (1995), Tyson (1995) and Storey (1994). This can indicate whether HR can give a more efficient progress in a business with a complex implementation of the principles such as culture, social, policies and other factors. In this case study of Marsya Farm will give the information needed to solve the key issues involved and using HR practices to counter and workout the problems and reinforce with a firmer management of its employees alongside the analytical framework of HR models particularly using The Fombrun Model (Fombrun et al., 1984). The model provides HRM characterization that defines the factors and relationships with researched variables. The model would help provide HRM practices with distinctive characteristics as well as to uphold some HR practices. In order to illustrate the essence and value of main HR activities, they help to explore and appreciate the universe. Having the support of analytical framework upon applying the HR practices to the organisation.

This case study talks about Marsya Farm, a farm that focus on the agriculture of Brunei. With more argipreneurs present in Brunei, Marsya Farm owner indicates an inspiring argipreneurs seek to aiming farming is the solution to a necessity to Brunei's resources. Marsya Farm is a business farm that mainly looks at agricultural innovation and experimenting them with traditional methods compared to modern innovations in agriculture techniques. These innovations are effective irrigation, fertigation, hydroponics and rain shelter and implanting them to a 2.8-hectare plantation of the farm. The farm contains wide variety of crops and fruits as assets and turning them to profit.

The paper then describes the implementation of HR model in assisting the business with a more developed system. Identifying the issues of HR in Marsya Farm and resolving with an analytical framework of the model. Therefore, the techniques that are used for validating the model and the HR practices.

By leaning towards the principles of Human Resources Management, it is important for an organisation to make the employees just as important as managing other systems. Marsya farms sees that HR practices is needed to sustain the business in a long run and to achieve its employees' capabilities. Marsya farm is emphasizing the need to produce a more sophisticated HR practices that able to assist the system of the business to give maximum business results and primarily protects its employee's morale and capabilities.

Body

In theory of HRM, it is always a concern in managing the people within organisation. Marsya Farms seeks to resolve any HR related issues by looking at 4 functions using The Frombun Model.

Fombrun Model

The Fombrun model specializes only on 4 positions and their interrelationships of the focuses. Marsya Farm should have the structure of the organisation and HR system that controls their management in a manner that is consistent with their strategy of organisations. This model emphasises on four aspects in terms of Selection, Appraisal, Rewards and lastly Human Resource Development which is all related to the efficiency of the organisation.

The Fombrun Model of HRM (1984)

As seen in the diagram the organisational effectiveness can be influenced through four key functions of the HRM. Fombrun is said to be the first model in HRM analytical tool framework to clarify the existence of the organisation's performance and helping to identify the key of HR activities around it. The model is simple and also stresses the relationships between the four functions and their mutual effects on the effectiveness of the organisation as it correlates one another. The Frombrun Model was formed in 1984 as a way to enhance organisation effectiveness and to adopt HRM principle that should be constantly practice. The HR perspective of Fombrun model is it focuses on the individuals and the organization performance output as a whole. It sees that the people can alter the effectiveness of the company in the four functions listed. This model is based on the strategic supervision to the employees and frameworks of hierarchical structures for people management. They prioritize in managing human capital to fulfill strategic objectives to produce the desired outcome. The HRM practice of the model is considered as hard HR and the model attempts to approach the period of human resources and strategic management and strain on the environment aspects of the employees.

Selection

The best influence in affecting effectiveness is the start of it all is selection in determining the hierarchy of the organisation. It is the process of finding a suitable individual who can complete the job required to be done effectively and provide the company with valuable contributions. The selection system relies on the job analysis of the potential employees to guarantee that requirements for the selection is related to the work given and can have substantial organizational value. Such selection requirements needed primarily looks at the KSAO which is knowledge, skills, abilities and other features including experiences. In order to identify the most eligible applicants, the selection process uses the evidence-based practice that involve the potential applicants as well as the people that are already in the company.

Appraisal

This relates to the performance appraisal that is a comprehensive measurement of the employees' performance and an appreciation of the individual's potential in their personal growth in the company and development. This is done by maintaining records for the assessment of pay arrangements, salary structure, wage increases specifically the staff needs. Additionally, consider the strengths and weaknesses of workers to bring the best men into the right work. The reason is to sustain and evaluate the potential for later growth and growth that is already present in the individual. Providing workers with input about their performance and associated status. Lastly, it acts as a framework for manipulating the staff's working habits as well as to study and maintain the curriculum of promotional and other training involved.

Rewards

Employees are human beings and taken into consideration of the needs of an individual, rewards are used as for their accomplishments and benefits earned by the workers of the organisation for their job performance. Supporting the organization's objectives by aligning employee objectives with the same targets that they must complete. To ensure that the company is capable of hiring and retaining sufficiently the amount of workers with the necessary skills. The objective to sync managers and workers' risk expectations with those of the organisation. They are also used to inspire workers and to obey with statutory regulations. It signifies that rewarding is essentially just an ethical concept to compensate for employee's work.

Human Resource Development

Human resource development is the development of the employees, a concept used to develop the workers in their KSAO through the progress of employee training and their personal career development that may affect the organisation's performance. It is important to improve workers by assisting in preparation, education, and growth to achieve successful performance. It focuses on the growth to provide and refine the skills that are related to the existing and potential employment of workers along with any upcoming organization's future activities or implementation. Human resource development seeks to improve talent growth and the willingness of an organisation to match staff with strategic preparation and job opportunities. These consist of training, career development and organisation efforts that are improved on to assist the workers to grow in learning new skills and change their way of performance level.

Discussion

Selection can be improved by picking out the potential high skilled workers. The start of an effective organization is when the right employees are picked for the job. Marsya Farm should focus on selecting the perfect candidate that are talented and know well enough in the field.

One of the issues that was present by Marsya Farm was the lack of expertise in the market. The reduction in knowledge and skills in youth community for agricultural abilities. With this problem there is a need to focus on the youth to develop their skills in agricultural relations. A program is introduced to the public, those that are passionate to study further into the agriculture industry are able to receive guidance and advices that can be retrieved from the program mentors. This allows a step forward for youth or potential agriculture business and even workers to enter the market. The program would let the development of skills and necessities to run agriculture field, Marsya Farm can more receive labor or skilled workers supply market to employ. This will make the recruitment and selection process to be

easier and much more efficient with the skilled candidates that are fit for the job. Marsya Farm will be able to pick the individuals that uphold the field qualifications needed to operate the farm. Additionally, the issue of not able to attract talented workers, with the increasing liable to influenced by job turnover nowadays that tend to be from the reputation of the business, wages and even culture. This can be countered if Marsya Farm can create attractive online presences that reflect the community, achievements and core values of their organization through the use of successful & sufficient HR software and HR resources. Developing a realistic recruitment strategy that take company priorities and competitive recruitment initiatives into account along with promoting employee engagement. Marsya Farm attempted to exposing the youths to commit themselves to agriculture at an early stage so they can enter the industry and somehow bring a benefit to the organisation i.e. higher number of candidates. More knowledgeable people from the agricultural education program can be implemented thus having high interest to take the job field in the future.

In achieving an effective organization means that employees should constantly perform up to the company's standard. This comes along the appraisal aspect in Marsya Farm, to measure the quantity and consistency of the work output of employees as well as to evaluate. Performance does impact the outcome as some employees in Marsya Farm may not perform well and some producing zero efforts. Productivity has to be highlighted and this is done by giving frequent feedbacks to employees. Employees are supervised and they tend to work much more efficiently when being monitored with attention. Workers are able to take in any advises or feedbacks whether it would be positive or criticisms from the managers. If well implemented, it can enhance their way of executing the job tasks.

There will always be an issue with employee retention even for the people in Marsya Farm, the effectiveness can be affected if Marsya Farm fails to measure it is the overall hiring efficiency of the people working in the company. This means that an organisation should have a satisfying working atmosphere for the employees. With this said, the less people are expected to abandon their job if they are more comfortable with the working environment based on their safety, health and security. It is often not easy to the retain the employees because people would just look for a higher pay than their current salary and they usually take when they have the opportunity.

Therefore, reward management is necessary in which rewards can act as a motivator for workers. The HR manager can discuss and decides what they can reward to the employees as a compensation for their work whether it is intrinsic or extrinsic. For instance, money or promotions can inspire them to be more productive in work. It is also the job of Marsya Farm management to ensure that the employees are reviewed to decide who is worthy of the reward. Rewards can also be in a form of recognition as they are being displayed to the public to allow an increase in happiness and their self esteem to produce a promising result. It is believed that the more encouragement is given the likely a person would perform well.

To further making an effective organisation is the Human Resource Development. Marsya Farm management believes that strengthening their employees in their commitment involvement and their performance will indeed affect a better outcome. The development of employees is achievable if there is a training and more education to develop their KSAO. When they are more trained and gained enough experience for the workforce, they can raise the job satisfaction of the employees as it is always what an employer would want. An improving dynamic workforce environment in the organisation to be ready in any circumstances. Getting constant feedback from employees also helps to improve the program. Positive reinforcement by using the verbal reaffirmation in rewarding the staff who demonstrate success in job task that may motivate them further to be continuous learner. The lack of information is also a factor in which there should be manageable quantities of information. Giving employees information so they are able to exercise and apply the information to their work. Moreover, the lesson that they learnt can be taken into the next training session with to further their development and relevant advices on improvement.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Although Fombrun discusses that it is only prescriptive, it ignores the interests of stakeholders, situational considerations and strategic option notions together with the expression of the continuity and the value of relating the internal HR policies to external business strategy. It does only limit to 4 functions to approach and are overlooked other factors. There are several elements to a more successful organisation performance. This include both environmental view and contingency variables that affect HR functions. The model is a requirement for HR practices in many industries and it aims to establish a deeper understanding of HRM and combines HRM and company strategy. Marsya Farm has enforced the HR policies of recruiting, selection, employee welfare enforced and many more. Selections were evaluated carefully in picking the best by the experiences gained from different sources. The retention of the workers is crucial and one of the most critical fundamental concerns to be discussed. Rewards policies were adopted in the company. Trainings were done to develop the employees further and keep them up to standard. Even with just using The Fombrun Model it is much more effective in combining all models of HRM and will lead to a sustainable human resource.

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